

TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF THE ORAL CAVITY

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Abstract. *Prevention is a set of activities of state, social, hygienic, medical institutions aimed at maintaining the health of the population and preventing diseases. Its main purpose is to prevent the causes and conditions that cause diseases and to strengthen the body.*

Keywords: *tooth, caries, prevention, stomatologist, oral hygiene, toothbrush, toothpaste.*

First of all, let's understand the word Caries (lat. caries - rot) - a dental disease (see Caries) [1]. Caries is a common disease that affects 95% of the population. Caries is a complex pathological process in which tooth tissue is quickly or slowly destroyed and a damaged cavity – a cavity – is formed in the tooth. Currently, there are several hundred theories about the origin of caries. Caries is caused by many factors. Key factors include:

- microflora of the oral cavity;
- nutrition and diet;
- amount of fluorine in water;
- composition and volume of saliva;
- general condition of the body;
- extreme effects on the body;
- endogenous and exogenous factors of the external and internal environment.

There are three types of caries: anatomical, topographical and clinical. The anatomical classification mainly consists of enamel caries, dentin caries, cementum caries. According to the depth of the disease, the topographic classification is divided into: spotted caries, superficial caries, medium caries and deep caries. According to the clinical course, fast and slow caries are distinguished. According to the clinical picture, white and pigmented spots (from brown to brown) are distinguished. During examinations, it turned out that caries is white with rapid progression and pigmented with slow progression. The progression of caries is of great importance when drawing up a treatment plan.

Causes of dental caries

Determining whether you have tooth decay is very easy. Changes in the color of the tooth surface (the stain can be dark or liquid) or its structure, for example, roughness, are symptoms indicating the onset of a disease. Also, a sign of caries is toothache when eating, especially severe pain that occurs under the influence of sweets, hot and cold. Bad breath can also be a symptom of the disease. If the disease has progressed to the middle stage, a cavity has appeared in the tooth - usually it is easily palpable with the tongue. However, the “hole” does not arise only due to caries; only a dentist can make an accurate diagnosis.

TREATMENT OF DENTAL CARIES

If caries is in the staining stage, adequate saturation of the teeth with fluoride and calcium is sufficient to eliminate it. If the disease is superficial, medium or deep, there is probably no other way to do without using a car. To treat caries, it is necessary to saw off the damaged part of the tooth and restore its natural shape using filling materials. Treatment for deep tooth decay usually

requires two visits to the dentist: first a temporary filling and then a permanent filling. If caries appears under a filling, radiography is used to identify it.

There are two main methods of caries treatment: non-invasive (“without sawing”) and invasive (with sawing of the affected tissue). The choice of method depends on the stage of the disease.

CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT WITHOUT PILLS

This processing does not involve sawing. This method is used if the disease is in the initial stage, i.e. the color of the enamel has changed or there are characteristics of the patient’s body (for example, an allergic reaction to painkillers).

The essence of the non-invasive method is to remove soft enamel and mineralization. Treatment is carried out in several stages: examination, separation from the gums and application of the necessary materials. The duration of the procedure is about an hour, depending on the equipment and skills of the dentist. If the treatment is carried out efficiently, then with proper dental care the disease will not recur. However, if the patient does not give up his bad habits, the doctor is not to blame.

PROCESSING OF HARD TISSUE BY SAWING

Treatment of affected areas of the tooth using anesthesia. The stages of treatment depend on the stage of the disease.

Medium caries is treated according to the following scheme:

- Analgesia;
- Mechanical and medicinal treatment;
- Installation of protective coating;
- Restoration of the anatomical shape of the tooth using filling materials;
- Grinding and finishing.

In case of deep caries, before installing the coating, it is necessary to check the degree of damage, that is, how close the affected pulp is to the surface. This is done to ensure that there is no pain after treatment. The duration of treatment for medium and deep caries lasts one hour, sometimes up to two hours. Medium caries, as we said earlier, is usually treated in one visit, while deep caries requires two visits to the dentist, and in severe cases - three or more times. The effectiveness of treatment depends on the quality of the drugs used, the qualifications of the specialist and the characteristics of the body. With poor nutrition and poor hygiene, as well as weak immunity, the disease may recur after some time.

MODERN TREATMENT METHODS

One of the modern approaches to the treatment of caries is the chemical-mechanical method. This method involves placing special instruments in the area of the affected tooth and then removing and filling the affected part of the tooth. The advantages of this method are that it is painless and does not require deep sawing.

Pathological tissue can also be removed by strong spraying of air or water using special powders. But this method is effective only in the initial stages of caries. Damaged areas can also be removed with a laser. It recognizes the affected tissue and vaporizes it. Such modern methods, of course, do not cause much discomfort and are painless, but such procedures can be very expensive for the patient.

PREVENTION OF CARIES

Until now, the causes of caries have not been fully established. There are three factors that cause caries:

1. Microorganisms of dental caries;
2. Sweets;
3. Fluoride deficiency.

The impact of these three factors leads to a decrease in the intensity of caries. To reduce the intensity of caries, it is necessary to clean the tooth of caries, reduce sweets in the daily menu, and eliminate fluoride deficiency.

The use of toothpastes in the prevention of oral caries.

There are types of modern toothpastes that have hygienic and medicinal properties. In turn, healers are divided into toothpastes that have an effect on inflammation and have preventive properties. Inflammatory agents are divided into salt-storing agents and according to biological activity. Those with preventive properties are divided into fluorine-preserving and mineral-preserving. In addition, there are also whitening toothpastes. Usually people go to the store and buy the pasta that suits them in price and size, or the first one they come across. In fact, pastes should be chosen according to the doctor's recommendation, depending on the condition of the teeth, whether there are diseases or not. Those who do not have dental problems can easily use regular hygienic pastes. From the water we drink to the place we live; it plays an important role in our dental health. The main substance necessary for teeth is fluoride. We get it from the food we eat and the water we drink. If the water in some areas does not contain or lacks this substance, it is recommended to use toothpaste with fluoride. If on the contrary, you don't have to use such toothpastes. Additionally, flossing is an effective way to remove debris from between your teeth and gums.

Rules for brushing your teeth. It is advisable to brush your teeth twice a day - morning and evening, after meals. For example, some people brush their teeth before breakfast and continue with their day. Brushing your teeth when you wake up in the morning is a good idea. Some people make this choice for the sake of aesthetics, while others make this choice because it is convenient for them. But rinsing after eating helps remove various debris stuck on the bases of the teeth. Food residues in teeth lead to various dental diseases, starting with caries.

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